

Political Manipulation of Nigeria's Pluralistic Society: The Role of African Traditional Religion

Iliya Moses Katung

Department of Christian Religious Studies, Kaduna State University, Kaduna, Nigeria

Abstract

Nigeria is known to be a pluralistic society in view of the diverse religious and ethnic groups that have been coexisting for over a century. While plurality should be a source of strength, politicians have been manipulating it to their advantage. Consequently, incompetent and unqualified people have always found themselves in the corridors of power at the detriment of the competent and qualified. This paper explores political manipulation in Nigeria's pluralistic society, its impact, and the place of African Traditional Religion in the system. The historical and descriptive methods are employed in this study and findings reveal that right from independence, the political class has always capitalized on ethnicity and religion as a manipulative weapon to win election and remain in power in spite of their anti-people's policies. The study further reveals that African Traditional Religion, one of the three known religions in Nigeria, has always enjoyed a political system that is free from manipulation due to its structure that is built on honesty and the belief in the choice of the supernatural in every vacant position. However, the same cannot be said about Christianity and Islam as most adherents of the two religions are caught in the web of political manipulation as evident in recent general elections in Nigeria. This study recommends that the Nigerian society should learn from the virtue of honesty and total submission to the will of God in the choice of leaders as strictly practiced in African Traditional Religion.

Keywords: Political Manipulation, Pluralistic Society, African Traditional Religion

Introduction

The developed countries of the world are propelled to their status by political will and nationalism. Political leaders in these countries build on structures that hold leaders accountable for their actions or inactions while in office. With this scenario, a high level of patriotism is noticed amongst citizens of these countries because political leaders lead by example. A country's unity is preached and practiced due to its invaluable role in the growth and development. In his inaugural speech on 20 January, 1961, John F. Kennedy said: "Ask not what America will do for you, but what, together, we can do for the freedom of man."¹ This speech has inspired millions of Americans and prompted in them the spirit of patriotism. Contrarily, African countries that are mostly under-developed are characterized with self-serving leadership model. Political leaders in Africa deliberately promote division amongst the citizens in a bid to perpetuate themselves in office without accountability. But the growth and development of any society are dependable on societal unity, patriotism and political will. These attributes are conspicuously missing in most African countries, hence the years of under-development.

Nigeria is one of the leading countries in the African continent and one of the under-developed countries in the world. As a country blessed with human and natural resources, it is expected to be one of richest countries in the world. The country is blessed with vast arable land, huge deposit of mineral resources, and adequate rainfall for farming as well as vast water bodies for irrigation farming. With these, Nigeria has no business being poor.² It is ironical, however, that the country is counted as one of the poorest countries in the world, with all the attributes of a poor country visibly noticed: poor infrastructure, poor health care, lack of adequate industries, high rate of unemployment, dwindling economy and other indices signifying poverty.³ Owing to this poor state, the citizens are vulnerable to moral decadence, diseases and poor state of living. The paradoxical state of Nigeria being blessed with human and natural resources, yet poor and under-developed can be traced to poor leadership. It is believed that visionary leadership and good governance remain the hallmark of propelling the wheels of growth and development in any society.

This is obviously missing in the Nigerian context and the institutions saddled with the responsibility of checking the excesses of the executive is not living to expectation. There seems to be harmonious relationship amongst politicians at all level of governance, and for many years the political class continues to plunge the country into an inexcusable state of poverty with impurity. Poor leadership has been a problem in Nigeria because the political class has found a way of exploiting the pluralistic nature of the country to their advantage. The Nigerian population is divided along tribal, regional and religious lines. Sentiments along these divides are so high and this has played out in the hands of the politicians who are willing to further promote the division and hatred as long as they help them remain politically relevant.

Many politicians in Nigeria find themselves in the corridors of power, not by their qualification or competence but by riding on the back of tribal, regional or religious sentiment. Irrespective of their performance in office, the Nigerian political leader is assured of protection from their tribe, region or religion when their stewardship is called to question. With this scenario, the political leaders continue to persist in their greed and lack of patriotism irrespective of party affiliation, level of governance, tribe, region or religion, thus the saying in Nigeria: all politicians are the same. But before the advent of democracy in Africa, leadership in traditional African society was selfless patriotic and exemplary. The choice of leaders and the art of leadership are done in strict adherence to traditionally acceptable pattern. Any deviation from the laid down pattern is met with instant and severe punishment with this, leaders in Traditional African Society do not take their position for granted. This paper is an exposition of the level of political manipulation in Nigeria's pluralistic society and the consequences on the populace. The paper also considers the Traditional African Society pattern of leadership which is indigenous to African as a possible solution to the under-development Nigeria is thrown into by manipulation of the diversity of the people.

Issues on Nigeria's Pluralism

Nigeria is a country in Western Africa. The country according to West African Gateway, sits on land area of 923 768 km² and it is the most populous country in Sub-Saharan Africa. Before the colonial era, there was no entity as Nigeria. But with the amalgamation of the Northern and Southern Protectorates in 1914, the country, Nigeria, came into limelight. For ease of governance, the country was divided into Northern Region, Southern Region and Eastern Region. These regions continued to exist after independence in 1960, but in 1963, the Midwestern Region was created, bringing the regions into four. Today Nigeria has 36 states with the Federal Capital, Abuja. During colonialism and early years of independence only regional affiliation were at the center stage, but with the creation of more states which came as a result of the clamour for self-actualization by many minority tribes, another dimension to pluralism was born. To fully comprehend how pluralism evolved in Nigeria it is imperative look at it from historical point of view and this will expose the different dimensions of pluralism from tribal, regional and religious dimensions.

Tribal Dimension

The amalgamation of Southern and Northern Protectorates in 1914 by Sir Fredrick Lugard gave birth to what is today known as Nigeria. Before then, the country comprised of diverse kingdoms, regions, nationalities and tribes each existing independently. There were major and centralized kingdoms like Benin, Oyo, Hausa land and Kanem Borno. These were well-structured kingdoms with well-organized system of governance.⁴ But there were so many mini-states known to be decentralized. These states included the Igbos, tribes in Plateau, Benua and a lot of others. In spite of some similarities in culture, each region, kingdom or group existed independently with their uniqueness. However, there was a trade relationship that existed amongst these independent groups before the advent of modern system. In affirming this commercial relationship, A. S. Ariyo states that: "During this early period, the concept of international trade is unknown. The movement of commodities, services and capitals across frontiers in exchange of products of state necessities or luxury values occurred in the form of long-distant trade

which was conducted over a complex network of overland and water routes across the frontiers of states and regions of West Africa and beyond.”⁵

Despite the independence of every kingdom, the inter-dependent nature of humans was exposed. Mostly, all kingdoms depended on others for the supplies of some basic needs or luxuries. For instance, kolanut was supplied to the North from the South. The kolanut plant was not grown in the North. Also, groundnuts, grains that are mostly grown in the North were supplied to the South. All these were done through long distant trade. Many kinds of currencies were used as medium of exchange including cloths, cowries, manila, iron rods, silver and gold. Some of them have limited area of acceptance while others were used over a vast area.⁶ Apart from the long distance trade, rivers within Nigeria, especially River Niger and River Benue fostered trade and cultural relationship among pre-colonial ethnic groups. For instance, there was a commercial interaction among Ijo, Igbo, Igala and Nupe along the banks of River Niger. Such interaction promoted peace and trust among members of these ethnic groups.⁷

There were also inter-tribal marriages. This was greatly influenced by closeness and trade interactions. “Marriage across ethnic boundaries helped to cement relationships. This type of marriage was particularly common among long distance travellers who embraced it for both commercial and diplomatic purposes.”⁸ All these were indication of long years of peaceful coexistence among the different ethnic groups that is today known as Nigeria. However, not all was rosy regarding the relationship among the regions and ethnic groups. The history of tribal and regional wars is well recorded. These conflicts were caused largely by land disputes, quest for dominance, territorial expansion, self-preservation and defense.⁹ As a result of frequent inter-tribal wars, African communities lived in fear and suspicion of their neighbours. This also promoted hostility and lack of cooperation. Although there are areas of peaceful relationships, apprehension and suspicion took the center stage. It was at this stage that the colonialists met the distinct communities that were later brought together as one Nigeria.

Regional Dimension

It must be borne in mind that before the colonial era, even larger linguistic groups like Yoruba, Hausa, Igbo were not united as one. The Yoruba’s were divided into many communities independent of the others. This was also applicable to Hausa and Igbo. But the colonial presence ushered in regional cooperation, thereby expanding the existing tribal pluralism to regional stage. The British colonial imposition took a gradual step with annexation of Lagos in 1861. That paved the way for their involvement in the development of the hinterland in Yoruba land. Similar strategy was employed in taking control of the Niger Delta. The British government also asserted her influence in the North and soon, the whole communities known as Nigeria to day fell under the total control of the British Government. By 1900, three geo-political administrations were inaugurated to mark the formal commencement of British rule in regions. There regions were the colony and protectorate of Lagos, the protectorate of Southern Nigeria and the protectorate of Northern Nigeria.¹⁰ From this stage, the tribal divide that existed pre-colonial era advanced to the regional stage. The regionalization was not meant to foster unity, cooperation or patriotism but a means for easy governance and administration by the British government. It is thus safe to say that uniting the people of the different ethnic groups was not the concern of the colonial master.

The amalgamation of the Southern and Northern protectorates in 1914 by Lord Frederick Lugard was never a Federal idea, but for commercial and administrative purposes of the colonialists. The amalgamation was done with total disregards to the differences in culture, religion, character and the socio-political traditions of the various ethnic groups.¹¹ The nationalist’s movement and the emergence of indigenous political parties clearly show a massive regional division in the country. Though the nationalist’s movement was meant to actualize self-rule, the pursuit of this noble aim was based on regional sentiment. The nationalists were carrying their regional bias in this move and so the political parties that emerged from inception had regional coloration. The pre-independence political parties served as a seed of ethnicity in Nigeria political space. For instance, the action Group developed from a Yoruba cultural Association, *Egbe omo Oduduwa*; the NCNC had its bias towards the Igbos while the NPC emerged from *Jamiyar arewa*. The leadership of these parties had ethnicity written on them:

Obafemi Awolowo for AG, Nnamdi Azikiwe for NCNC and Sir Ahmadu Bello for the NPC. Even as the struggle for independence continued, the country is so pluralized along tribal and regional divides. The independence that came in 1960 was a great achievement. Unfortunately, the country was handed to leaders and a people so divided with no political will for unity.

Religious Dimension

The regional dimension Nigeria politics took before independence continued after the independence in 1960. The battle for regional supremacy seemed to out-weigh the ethnic sentiment that has been in existence before the colonial era. The political actors of that period promoted regional agenda against a common one. Even the first military coup and the counter coup of 1966 bore the mark of regionalism.¹² This is not to suggest the absence of tribal affiliation or loyalty but that regional sentiment was at the center stage of Nigeria's political affairs. The June 12, 1993 general election gives credence to silent role of religion in the political affairs of the country. Moshood Abiola and Babagada Kingibe were the presidential candidates and running mates of the then SDP respectively despite both being Muslims. From the results announced before the annulment of the election, the SDP with a Muslim-Muslim ticket was matching to victory with a clear margin. Interestingly, the acceptance of the SDP candidate was overwhelming, cutting across states and regions of the country. Although there are signs of intolerance between the two major religions in the country, Christianity and Islam, from the 1970s, such did not lead to political divide.¹³ Subsequently, religion creeps into Nigeria politics in addition to the existing tribal and regional dimensions. The emergence of religion into Nigeria's political scene took a gradual step until it became pronounced in 1999.

Religion has become increasingly important to Nigerian politics due to political liberation linked to the return to civilian rule in 1999. This in addition to the autonomy granted to states in the federal system. This led to the introduction of Shari'a law in twelve states of the North.¹⁴ From this period onward, religion has been playing a very active role in the political space. Unfortunately, the roles played by the two major religions does not promote unity, peace and progress but division, chaos and ultimately, along with tribalism and regionalism give room for manipulation. Divided along tribal, regional and religious lines, the stage is set for an unhealthy manipulation.

Nigeria's Pluralism and Political Manipulation

As early mentioned, what is today known as Nigeria was a multi-ethnic society living independently. While some of these ethnic groups had established cultural and commercial relationships, others remained hostile to one another, hence the inter-ethnic wars that were so prevalent before the colonial incursion. The British, in their move to bring together these multi-ethnic communities into one country, felt that the people are better divided than united. For them, a divided people would be easily governed. Thus, nothing was done to give the various groups a sense of patriotism to one Nigeria. This deliberate act by the British colonialists paved the way for political manipulation in Nigeria. At the beginning, the manipulation was at the regional stage and in regional sentiment is promoted for electoral position, nomination and consideration of every government policy.

Such was the situation that led to the North declining to a motion for independence by Anthony Enahoro in 1956. According to Yakasai, the North declined because they lack the requisite man power to face the challenges of governance.¹⁵ The North at, that time, was clearly disadvantaged in terms of number of educated people in comparison to their Southern counterparts. In fairness to the political actors of pre-independent and the first republic, their regional manipulation was not born out of selfish or personal achievement but genuine concern for the interest of their regions. But soon, regional interest was totally sidelined for personal gains. Politicians began to sell tribal and regional sentiment to the electorate in their bid to be elected into political offices of their choice. Even in non-elective offices that are based on appointment, regional and tribal sentiments are used as bets to get appointed. Unfortunately people so elected or appointed do nothing for the betterment of those they used to get to the office. The situation took a worst turn when religion was brought on stage.

Section 10 of the 1999 Constitution stipulates that Nigeria is a secular state and no religion shall be adopted as a state religion. However, politicians have dragged in the two major religions, Christianity and Islam, into the game. This they achieved by sponsoring adherents of both religions to pilgrimage in defiance to the country's constitution. Today, this is seen as a right not a privilege by many adherents of these religions. In addition to sponsorship for pilgrimage, places of worship are built with state funds; monthly allowance given to clerics in some states and total sponsorship of religious programmes by political office holders. Consequently, political actors run to the church and mosques to campaign for votes. Clerics in both religions have become "campaign managers" for politicians who share same faith with them irrespective of their competence and qualification. Umeanolue gives substance to this when he claims that: "It is also an issue that voting and campaign, in some cases, are based on religious sentiment. In this case, religion could be used to either canvass support for a candidate or dissuade the electorate from voting for him or her. This is why some Christians will not support a Muslim candidate and vice versa."¹⁶ Religion has brought a different dimension to the already divided Nigeria society. With it, one can get votes across regions, not for their competence or capacity. Recent general elections in the country showed that Nigeria is greatly divided not just along tribal or regional divides but religious. As long as Nigeria pluralism keeps benefitting the average politicians, promoting the division is worth "investing" on.

Impact of Political Manipulation in Nigeria

Nigerian politicians have been manipulating the divisive nature of the populace to their advantage and the situation keeps escalating. There is nothing done to unite the people since those in authority see the divide as an advantage of selfish aim. Unfortunately, political manipulation that is prevalent in the country comes with negative consequences. These consequences have impeded the growth and development of the country in all areas. The impact of political manipulation is so grievous to the extent that even the future of the country looks uncertain. Lamenting over the danger of political manipulation of the country's pluralism, Oboh says: "It's a subject that is eating deep against the desired unity of our country. Most would agree that if not addressed, strategically, tribalism will continue to be used by some political juggernauts as a breeding ground for further divisions, contention and hatred."¹⁷

The effects of political manipulation due to the pluralism of the country are so enormous. Firstly, the country is further divided since it serves as a gain to the political class. The 2023 general election witnessed great divisiveness in Nigeria's political space. While some voted based on religious sentiment, others did because of regional sentiment. The politicians who stand to benefit from this continued to promote it. Politicians were seen paying visit to religious leaders asking for support, not by what they had to offer but on the premise of religious sentiment. In turn, many religious clerics bought into the idea and kept preaching on the need to vote a candidate of their faith without telling adherents what such candidate has to offer the society. The campaign of divide did not stop at the religious corridor alone but moved to regional and tribal stages where these sentiments were sold as the only bases on which the electorate should vote candidates.

As a result of this, it is extremely difficult for a candidate to get votes outside their tribe, region or religion. While the electoral situation is grossly divided, the politicians continue to fuel the flame of division and hate in a society that should be united for growth and development. Secondly, the campaign of division can only enthrone incompetent leaders since a thorough check of their antecedents was not given attention. Many believe that the problem of Nigeria is bad leadership but behind bad leadership is a bad process. The campaign that only promotes tribe, region or religion is one that does not mean well for a country that is in dire need of unity. Nigeria is endowed with capable and competent people, in all ethnic groups, regions and religions who can take the country out of the woods but these people are constantly sacrificed on the altar of tribal, regional or religious sentiment. Those who have nothing to offer but divisiveness continue to be saddled with leadership responsibilities when they have no business being there due to lack of capacity and competence.¹⁸

Thirdly, as a result of the enthronement of incompetent leaders, corruption and impunity thrive. Many politicians and appointees get to their position riding on the back of tribalism, sectionalism or religion. When leaders get to leadership position through manipulation, little or no achievement should be expected from them. It must be pointed out that aside divisive campaign by the political elite, other features that characterize Nigeria elections are vote buying, thuggery, ballot stealing and alteration of electoral figure. All these are undesirable for the growth of any society. But for the Nigerian society, they have become the foundation upon which leadership is built. With this, the state of endemic corruption is set. Political leaders in successive government continually promote policies that are nothing but self-serving. Financial corruption keeps increasing even in the face of constituted anti-corruption agencies like the EFCC and ICPC. But corruption in Nigeria is not about finances alone. Leaders in the country are known to promote nepotism and favoritism in terms of appointment with total disregards to merit. Abuse of office, indiscipline and disorder are gradually becoming a norm among leaders and followers alike. In fact, corruption has eaten into all facet of life in Nigeria.

The state of decadence is traceable to divisiveness which is preferred against unity. One thing that keeps fanning the flame of corruption in Nigeria is impunity. Corrupt leaders are never call to account and where they are, they “generate” sympathy from their tribe, region or religion.¹⁹ Bad leadership is viewed as one major problem of Nigeria but divisiveness is responsible for the sustenance of bad leadership as well as all forms of corruption related to it. In the face of such pluralism, the political class will continue to manipulate the system to achieve their selfish motive. The outcome of such pluralism and its manipulation is perpetual under-development and poverty.

African Traditional Religion and Political Manipulation

Although Christianity and Islam are the two dominant religions in Nigeria, it is well known that there exists Traditional African Religion along these two. It should be remembered that ATR is the indigenous religion of the Africans while Christianity and Islam were imported. While Christianity from the West, Islam came from the North African. These two dominant religions also play different roles in the political space in Nigeria. However, in view of the unhealthy politics in the country and the poor state of governance, the roles played by clerics of these faiths and their adherents have been called to question. Since both stand for moral uprightness and politicians run to churches and mosques to elicit votes, the fraternity between the two religions and the political class should have yielded good governance and healthy political atmosphere. Unfortunately this fraternity does not amount to sanity in the polity in Nigeria. Rather, there are clear indications that the introduction of these two religions in the polity has left the political water dirtier than it has been. Umeanolue, agrees with this when he opines that: ‘The influence of religion on politics has at various times threatened the cooperate existence of Nigeria.’²⁰ There is no doubt that politicians have found a way of manipulating the Christian faithful as well as Muslims in addition to the manipulation of tribes and region for selfish aim.

On the contrary, African Traditional Religion has never been mentioned in this manipulation. This suggests that there is something that stands them out. It is, therefore, pertinent and to study the political ideals and the pattern of governance in Traditional African Society. African Traditional Religion is the indigenous religion of the African people. It does not have a founder or date of inception and it does not distinguish between secular and religious life. In African Traditional Religion, everything is spiritualized.²¹ The choice of leaders in Traditional African Society does not follow the pattern of voting in a democratic setting but a traditionally laid down procedure that must be strictly followed. For example, in the Yoruba tradition, the role of the *Oba* is that of the father figure of the community. Apart from the fatherly role in the community, the *Oba* also has spiritual covering over his people on account of these, the choice of a king is a huge task on the king makers. One criterion that must be observed is invoking the gods to choose the king for the people. Thus, whoever emerges is believed to be choice of the gods and the people owe him absolute loyalty.²²

Similarly, choosing a king among the Oporomor community of Ijaw ethnic group is exclusively an affair of *Egbesi*, the Ijaw god of war. It means, therefore, that the stool is neither elective nor hereditary. But among the

Igbos, a centralized system of leadership did not exist. Every community is led by a group of elders and so power does not reside with a single person thus the saying: “*Igbo Enwe Eze*,” meaning the Igbo have no king. Interestingly, becoming an elder in the community is earned through bravery in war, heroic deeds in the community or long years of integrity.²³ While the system of attaining leadership position may differ from one society to another, African traditional society all over holds unto traditional laid down procedure in choosing leaders and the procedure are known to be objective, honest and transparent. This is conspicuously missing in the democratic system practiced in most African countries. Apart from the transparent and consistent way of choosing leaders in traditional African society, the system of governance is exemplary. A ruler in traditional African society is expected to lead with high sense of integrity and nothing short of that is acceptable. The leaders in this context live for their communities and thus lead selflessly.²⁴

Although leadership in Traditional African Society is a combination of autocracy and theocracy, there is no denying that the leaders guide their followers toward a course and their nationalism and patriotism are never put to question. Kings in Traditional Africa lead their communities to war, being at the forefront. Monarchs like Oba Ovonramwen Nogbesi, King Jaja of Opobo, Nana of Itshekiri were dethroned and deported by the colonialists for their uncompromising stand concerning their subjects. Leaders in African Traditional Society do not only have a pact with the led but with the gods and the ancestors and failure is met with dire consequences, not only upon the leader alone but along with his entire family. If African society and Nigeria enjoyed healthy political atmosphere in traditional society, why is the situation completely different today? In answering this question, Ezenweke and Kanu, point out that: “It is impossible to operate a political system that is primarily riddled with indiscriminate force, contempt for the will of the people, contempt for their traditional good values in governance if all the modern government arms legislature, executive and judiciary are imbued with these good traditional values, the hope for a sanitized values, the hope for a sanitized society will be satisfied.”²⁵ Kukah, supports this claim when he suggests that Nigerian total adoption of the foreign political experiment is largely responsible for the country’s predicament. He further argues that Western democratic models are not suitable for African realities.²⁶ The neglect of the traditional African pattern of politics which promotes credibility, patriotism, unity and openness for Western democracy that has left Nigerian society in a heterogeneous state, leaving the populace vulnerable to all forms of political manipulation.

Conclusion

The heterogeneous look of the Nigeria society, from colonial era, has been used for political manipulation. With attainment of independence, it was expected that the Nigeria political class would unite the citizens to promote patriotism to the Nigeria project. Unfortunately, the divisive politics continued in an alarming proposition. Politicians keep manipulating the Nigerian pluralism to win election and remain in office. The consequences of this manipulation are quite obvious in the country. If the country will get out of its present predicament, a trace of the root cause of the problem is needed, and this can be traced to the intentional ploy by colonialists to keep the people divided for their gains. This ploy was inherited by the indigenous politicians as a manipulative tool against fellow Nigerians. Political manipulation shows lack of patriotism and it is the worst kind of betrayal that has hindered the growth and development of the country. Interestingly, traditional African pattern of politics and governance can be emulated in order to change the narrative. Getting out of this leadership system that has kept the country in retrogression will require a consideration of the traditional political system, which was credible, transparent and consistent.

Endnotes

¹J. F. Kennedy, Presidential Inauguration Address <https://www.achieves.govt>

²M. A. Ayinla & B. Ogunmeru, “Youths Unemployment on Nigeria’s Economic Development,” in *Journal of Economic and Sustainable Development*, (2018):22-42.

- ³T. C. Ijere, "The State, Governance and Socio-Economic Development Realities," in Nigeria," in *Public Policy and Administrative Research*, (2014). 14.
- ⁴B. O. Egbe & I. O. Okoi, "Pre-Colonial Inter-Group Boundary Relations in Africa: The Nigerian Experience," in *Journal of Contemporary Research*, (2018): 64-75.
- ⁵A. S. Ariyo, "Trade across Frontiers: An Overview of International Trade before the Advent of Modern Economic System in Nigeria," in *Historia Actual*, (2014):53-60.
- ⁶Y. Abubakar & U. A. Yandaki, "From Commodity to Colonial Currency: A History of Money in the Former Sokoto Province of Nigeria during Pre-Colonial and Colonial Periods," in *African Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, (2022): 59-78.
- ⁷C. S. Ecoma & E. N. Ota, "The Presentness of the Past: Pre-Colonial Inter-Ethnic Relations and the Challenges of National Integration in Contemporary Nigeria," in *Saudi Journal of Humanities and Social science*, (2021): 277-284.
- ⁸Ibid.
- ⁹G. C. Aro et al, "Warfare in Pre-Colonial Africa: An Examination of the Role of Blacksmith," in *Trames Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, (2021): 67-82.
- ¹⁰T. Odowobi, "From Conquest to Independence: Nigerian Colonial Experience," in *Historia Actual Online*, <http://www.academia.edu>
- ¹¹C. O. Uwaifo, "Ethnicity and the Development of Political Parties in Nigeria," in *Journal of Poverty, Investment and Development*, (2016). 52.
- ¹²O. George, O. Owoyemi and S. Shadare, "Military Intervention in the Nigerian Politics: A Timed Bomb Waiting to Explode," in *International Journal of Business, Humanities and Technology*, (2012): 191-198.
- ¹³I. Gajere, *Religious and Ethnic Violence in Northern Nigeria*, (Pylar-Mark Publishers).
- ¹⁴A. Oladeji, I. Nolte and N. Danjibo, Religion, Politics and Governance in Nigeria, <http://www.researchgate.com>
- ¹⁵T. Yakasai, "Why North Rejected Enahoro's 1956 Independence Motion," *Punch Newspaper* (December 31, 2020). 10.
- ¹⁶I. L. Umeanolue, "Religious Influence on Politics in Nigeria: Implication for National Development," in *A New Journal for African Studies*, (2020): 76-87.
- ¹⁷M. Oboh, "Tribes, Nigeria and Divisive Politics," in *Vanguard Newspaper*, (August 17, 2022). 18.
- ¹⁸E. O. Akubor, "politics and Politicians in Nigeria: Establishing the Nexus Between Actors and their Action and Nation Building", <http://www.researchgate.net>
- ¹⁹A. Abubakar et al, "Corruption in the Nigerian Public Sector: An Impediment to Good Governance and Sustainable Development," in *Review of Public Administration and Management*, (2012): 59-78.
- ²⁰Umeanolue
- ²¹C. O. Ugwu & L. E. Ugwueye, *African Traditional Religion: A Prolegomenon* (Lagos: Merit International Publication, 2004).
- ²²A. Olaiya & O. Oladosu, "Kingship and Integrity in Yoruba Traditional Society," in *Nigerian Journal of Christian Studies*, (2021):168-188.
- ²³D. Eze, "Evolution of Kingship System among the Igbos of Nigeria," in *Academic Journal*, (2016).
- ²⁴Olaiya & Oladosun, 168-188.
- ²⁵E. O. Ezenweke & A. I. Kanu, "A Hermeneutical Approach to African Traditional Religion, Theology and Philosophy," in *Journal of African Studies and Sustainable Development*, (2021): 33.
- ²⁶M. H. Kukah, *Democracy and Civil Society in Nigeria* (Lagos: Spectrum Books Limited, 1999).